

The Role of Discourse Markers on Students' Comprehension of Academic Lectures (At Farsan College)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 25, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 31, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Academic Lectures, Students, Researcher</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7036110</p>	<p><i>This study attempts to investigate D.M and difficulties of listening to lectures. Students find problems in understanding lectures quickly because they don't know D.M. This study used the quantitative method by giving subjects a passage to read and questionnaire to answer. The researcher found that the students commit mistakes and found difficulties in recognizing D.M.</i></p>

Introduction

1. Definition of Discourse Markers

The general definition:-

Is a word or phrase that is relatively syntax-independent and does not change the truth conditional meaning of the sentence ,and has a some what empty meaning.

Micheal Swan defines "discourse markers" , " as

a word or expression which shows the connection between what is being said and the wider context ." For him , a discourse marker is something that either connects a sentence to what comes before or after, or indicates a speaker's attitude to what he is saying.

Statement of Problem :-

- 1-The students do not understand the lecture because there are no discourse markers .
- 2-The students do not comprehend lectures because they do not know the English D.M.
- 3-Students find difficulties in listening to lectures due to their misunderstanding of discourse markers .
- 4- Students do not exploit the strating of English as a second language .

Objectives or aims:-

The goals of this study can classified as follows:

- 1- to investigate Discourse markers in English writing.
- 2 –to study the usage of Discourse markers in English lectures .
- 3-to propose the best methods of note-taking by using Discourse markers and best strategies of lecture note - taking.

Literature Review :-

In this chapter , the researcher will discuss Discourse Markers .

Discourse Markers, are expression such as those in bold in the following sequences :

- 1-A:I like him. B:**So**, you think you'll ask him out then.
- 2-John can't go. **And** Mary can't go either.
- 3-Will you go? **Furthermore**, will you represent the class there ?
- 4-Sue left very late. **But** she arrived on time.
- 5-I think it will fly. **After all**, we built it right.

Discourse markers appeared before 25 years. An early reference to DMs as a linguistic entity was made by Lavol and Fanshel (1977:156) in discussing a question by Rhoda that began with well. The first and most detailed effort is that reported in Sheffrin (1987), who is concerned with elements which mark sequentially-dependent units of discourse. She labels them as discourse markers and analyzes in detail the expressions and,

because, but , I mean, now, oh, or, so, then, well, and you know as they occur in unstructured interview conversation.

List of discourse markers :-

Cause / effect	Comparison	Contrast	Addition
Whenever	likewise	although/but	also
as / as result	similarly	Alternatively	and/and then
Because	equally	besides/ despite	in addition
Consequently	as with	However/yet	moreover
Hence	Compared to	Nevertheless	too
Since	equivalent to	on the other hand	further
So		on the contrary	furthermore
Thus		Whereas	again
there for		while /whilst	the following
Accordingly		in contrast	what is more
Until		Otherwise	as well as
		Conversely	

Examples	Conclusion	Time
for example	According	as soon as
for instance	in brief	at the same time
in other words	in short	as long as
in effect	in conclusion	at length/at lest
in this case	on the whole	mean while
in particular	to sum up	secondly/ once
Specifically	Throughout	first of all/ first (ly)
such as	in all	finally/ eventually
in the case of	over all	initially / next
to show that	in summary	after (word)
Significantly	to conclude	subsequently
		henceforth

Styles of academic lecture :-

Academic lecture, as one type of academic discourse, is an important part of most university fields worldwide. The ability to comprehend academic lectures in English is thus an important need for university students.

As a definition of academic lectures have been identified as a register distinct from written text or conversation (Flowerdew, 1994; MacDonald et al.; 2000; Morell, 2004). Obviously, lectures tend to be monologic and relatively planned with respect to the content. Still a certain amount of adjustment and unplanned speech can be evident, indicative of the lecturer's awareness of listener's presence and needs and this can be attributed to (Chaudron, 199). With the status of English as an international language and the expansion in the use of English an increasing number of second language learners are engaged in academic pursuits that require them to listen to and comprehend great amounts of second language input.

Academic lecture, as one type of academic discourse, is an important part of most university fields worldwide. The ability to comprehend academic lectures in English is thus important need for university student. In recent years, applied linguists working in academic settings have increased our knowledge concerning academic listening tasks and their significance for second language teaching and learning.

Some researchers have dealt with the macro structure of lectures , others have analyzed the rhetorical function of introductions , others with interactional practices of lecture comprehension, and yet others have investigated

the use of specific variables in lectures. Flowerdew (1994) can be the most comprehensive publisher on this topic which includes specific papers dealing with cognitive discourse, ethnographic and pedagogical issues involved in academic listening and lecture comprehension.

The use of discourse markers in academic lectures has been investigated by other scholars. A prominent characteristic of lectures is the use of certain lexical phrases or rhetorical markers which help to signal the major content and sequence in argument, and to demarcate boundaries of non-essential information. These have attracted researchers' attention both for their inherent usefulness in understanding the structure of the discourse, and as potential aids in training listeners to understand better (Chaudron & Richards, 1986; Flowerdew & Tauroza, 1995; Morell, 2004). Nattinger & Decarrico (1992) display at some length the differences in such forms between less and more formal lecture styles, making the further distinction between "global" and "local" macro-organizers. Strodt-Lopez (1991) shows that asides, which have identifiable markers, are important features of lectures that maintain audience-speaker rapport and may in fact clarify the speaker's orientation to the main points. Discourse markers signal the information structure of discourse by emphasizing directions and relations within discourse.

Nonetheless, the research regarding the role of discourse markers in listening comprehension is meager (Perez & Macia, 2002). The present study therefore focuses on the use of discourse markers in academic lectures in an EFL setting. Thus, we are dealing with a context of language learning that has not been the focus of most academic lecture comprehension studies.

Listening difficulties lecture:-

Predicating the themes and vocabulary of a lecture before you listen can help to improve your comprehension of difficult listening segments.

First, look at the title of the lecture and any other clues you have (photos, maps, charts, outlines, etc.) and think of specific questions you think might be answered in the lecture. Next, think about possible answers to each of your questions. Discuss the questions with partner, if possible. Here are a few sample questions for lecture 4,

How to Give a Lecture.

1. What are necessary steps to prepare for a lecture ?
2. What are some techniques for delivering a lecture well ?
3. How many main points can a lecture have ?

Can you think of other question? If you have trouble thinking of questions, consider the major question words (who, what, when, where, why, how) and ask yourself how they might apply to the lecture topic. Creating these "prediction questions" will help you maintain your focus during lectures. In addition, the answers to the questions you form during this pre-listening step will often correspond to the actual main ideas of the lecture; in this way, these questions actually improve comprehension by helping you to identify main idea and discriminate them from less important details. (Note: This pre-listening strategy can also help you prepare for other listening situations, such as meetings, interviews, and any other instance in which you have clues to the content.)

You can use this prediction strategy during the lecture as well. That is, as often as you can, try to predict what kinds of information might come next. Even if some of your predictions are incorrect, this strategy will help you stay focused and give you a better chance of general comprehension.

Second, try to predict vocabulary you may hear in the lecture. To do this, you can analyze the main words in the title of the lecture. A dictionary and thesaurus will be very helpful.

Methodology

The number of subjects who participated in the Questionnaire is ten students from Farsan College, English Language Department. At the beginning, a passage was given to them to underline the D.Ms. In the passage the number of D.M is (33) and the result was as follows :-

Analysis of results :

Table of result :

	Student1	Student2	Student3	Student4	Student5
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	
And	✓		✓	✓	✓
e.g.					
That					
That					
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
That					
And					✓
e.g.					
Conversely				✓	

And				✓	✓
That					
And	✓		✓		✓
For			✓	✓	
That					
That					
And	✓		✓	✓	✓
And	✓		✓	✓	
e.g.					
And	✓		✓	✓	
e.g.					
And					
And	✓		✓		✓
But			✓	✓	✓
e.g.					
And	✓		✓	✓	✓
Again			✓		
And	✓		✓	✓	✓
For			✓	✓	✓
And	✓				✓
That					
And			✓		✓

	Student6	Student7	Student8	Student9	Student10
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
And	✓	✓			✓
And	✓	✓		✓	✓
e.g.					
That	✓				
That					
And	✓	✓		✓	✓
That					
And	✓	✓	✓		✓
e.g.					
Conversely					
And	✓	✓			✓
That					
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
For		✓		✓	
That					
That					
And	✓	✓	✓		
And			✓		✓
e.g.					
And	✓		✓		
e.g.					
And	✓		✓		✓
And	✓				✓
But	✓		✓		✓
e.g.					
And	✓				✓
Again					
And	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
For	✓	✓	✓		
And	✓				✓

That					
And	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table of result :

	The correct answer	The rate of correct answer	The incorrect answer	The rate of in correct answer
And	10	100%	0	0%
And	7	70%	3	30%
And	8	80%	2	20%
e.g.	0	0%	10	100%
That	1	10 %	9	90% 90
That	0	0 %	10	100%
And	9	90%	1	10%
That	0	0 %	10	100%
And	5	50%	5	50%
e.g.	0	0%0	10	100%
Conversely	1	10%	9	90%
And	5	50 %	5	50%
That	0	0%	10	100%
And	8	80 %	2	20%
For	4	40%	6	60%
That	0	0%	10	100%
That	0	0%	10	100%
And	7	70%	3	30%
And	5	50 %	5	50%
e.g.	0	0%	10	100%
And	5	50 %	5	50%
e.g.	0	0%	10	100%
And	0	0%	10	100%
And	8	80%	2	20%
But	8	80%	2	20%
e.g.	0	0%	10	100%
And	9	90%	1	10%
Again	1	10%	9	90%
And	9	90%	1	10%
For	8	80%	2	20 %
And	7	70%	3	30%
That	0	0 %	10	100%
And	7	70 %	3	30%

Total of answer =330 - Total of correct answer =141

Total of incorrect answer=189

The rate of correct answer = $141/330 \times 100 = 42,727\%$.

The rate of incorrect answer= $189/330 \times 100 = 57,273\%$.

Analysis:-

The question	I agree	I disagree	Not sure	I don't know
1-The teacher uses D.M.	10			
2-English has many D.M.	8	2		
3-I know the D.M.	7		3	
4-I understand the relationship between D.M. and understanding lectures.	8		2	
5-I have problems in understanding lectures.		7	4	
6-the lecturer is able to explain the lecture clearly.	7	1	1	1
7-the lecture style attracts students to learn.	5	1	4	

8-The pronunciation of the lecture makes it difficult to understand the lectures.	5	3	1	1
9-After knowing the discourse markers, I am able to understand easily lectures.	8		1	1
10-All lectures must contain D.M.	6		3	1

From the above result , the statistical calculation indicates that number of students who answer correctly is 57% and the incorrect number of students is 43%. This good result is due the exposure of students to know D.M from the beginning in the course of academic writing and the insistence of the lecturer in introducing these D.M by naming and classifying .This is also asserted by the answers of the questionnaire in which all the students agree in the usage of D.M by lecturers and the difficulty of understanding lectures without D.M.

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Abstract:-

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Recommendations for further research:-

The investigation of D.M and listening's difficulties to lectures is a vast area of research therefore , the following recommendations are suggested :-

1-Lecturers must teach students from the beginning the D.M and their usage.

2-The students must be taught strategies of note –taking and methods of listening to different styles of lectures.

Suggestions and implications of the study:-

The study has important and far – reaching implications for numerous specialists: the pedagogue , the classroom practitioner and the course designer .For the pedagogue , the research is more useful to provide better methods of introducing the D.M. More important are the implications for language classroom practitioner and the course designer to maximize students' comprehension of lectures in academic setting by using macro- and micro D.M and suitable listening strategies.

The Role of Discourse Markers on Students' comprehension of Academic Lectures (At Farsan Collage)

دور علامات الخطاب على الطلاب في فهم المحاضرات الأكاديمية (في كلية فرسان)

الخلاصة :-

تسعى هذه الدراسة إلى التحقيق في علامات الخطاب و صعوبة الاستماع إلى المحاضرات . الطالبات يواجهن مشاكل في فهم المحاضرات بسرعة ، و ذلك لأنهن لا يعرفن علامات الخطاب . هذه الدراسة تستخدم قطعة لقراءتها و استبيان للإجابة . حيث وجد الباحث أن الطالبات يرتكبن الأخطاء و يواجهن مشاكل في تعريف علامات الخطاب .

توصيات لإجراء مزيد من البحوث :-

الاقتراح والتوصيات هي :-

1 - يجب على المحاضرون تدريس الطلاب علامات الخطاب و استخدامها.

2 - يجب أن يتعلم الطلاب استراتيجيات اخذ الملاحظات في المحاضرات .

الاقتراحات والتوصيات :-

لهذه الدراسة آثار هامة و بعيدة المدى . فائدة البحث للمربي بتوفير أفضل الطرق لتعريف علامات الخطاب ، و الأكثر أهمية لمدرسي اللغة ولمصممي المناهج لاستخدام علامات الخطاب الكلية و الجزئية و استراتيجيات الاستماع المناسبة

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